

CryoCloud: Accelerating Discovery for NASA Cryosphere Communities with Open-Cloud Infrastructure

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Relevant NASA SMD Scientific Divisions: NASA Earth Science Division

Response to Aspect 1, the question on user needs and use cases for scientific data and computing in support of Open Science at SMD

NASA has started transitioning its expanding constellation of datasets to the cloud in service of meeting its goals laid out in the Open-Source Science Initiative. Transitioning to cloud-computing environments empowers researchers to effectively collaborate through persistent and dynamic workflows, forming an obvious platform for both collaborative research and a technical analysis hub. CryoCloud (cryointhecloud.com) is a NASA-funded project with the mission of providing training infrastructure to enable cloud-based workflows in a cohesive, ingestible experience. CryoCloud presents a generic infrastructure tailored to NASA Cryosphere research communities with the goals of building community cloud-computing standards and tools that are transferable to other communities of practice while demonstrating the value and interoperability of cloud-based workflows within the NASA data product ecosystem. *The following RFI shares the vision of the CryoCloud leadership team, the preliminary successes of the program debut, and the challenges going forward to implement cloud-computing platforms across NASA SMD scientific divisions.*

Cloud Computing to Build Open Science Practices and Enhance Scientific Impact

With a rapidly expanding data volume and a need to provide more connected streams of information to the public, NASA has implemented the Open-Source Science Initiative and migrated its datasets to the cloud, allowing for instantaneous and centralized access to multiple datasets. To fully leverage these new data formats and tools, researchers will need to transition to working in cloud-computing environments. These cloud-computing systems accommodate all scales of jobs, are fast and affordable with improved parallelization options, and store large volumes of data near computing architecture. Switching to the cloud provides the added benefit of lowering entry barriers to data access and use for all users, especially those who are under-served, and elevating scientific collaboration, innovation, reproducibility, and transparency. The migration of much of NASA's data catalog to the cloud makes this transitional moment ripe for expansive research progress and for developing the community's data-intensive future.

Substantial barriers currently exist for individual users and research groups to make the transition from their local systems to the cloud. During a cloud-computing panel at the May 2022 ICESat-2 Science Team Meeting, active ICESat-2 researchers expressed a handful of assumed or experienced barriers with their cloud transition: requiring more funds for cloud computing may leave scientists at a disadvantage in grant writing; cloud-computing can sometimes be slower than local clusters; cloud-based tools are not widely known or understood; AWS instance setup can be unintuitive and complex or inflexible; documentation is poor; and thousands of dollars can be accidentally spent. Scientists at the meeting shared sentiments that they were frustrated by the technical demands involved with setting up and maintaining built computing ecosystems, data types, and data management in addition to their scientific work, essentially assuming software

engineering roles in order to keep up with scientific needs. Innovative cloud solutions openly exist that mitigate or eliminate these challenges, but were not widely known to the scientific community.

To address these issues, we established a curated cloud-computing environment, called CryoCloud, in partnership with the International Interactive Computing Collaboration (2i2c), a non-profit with the mission to provide open-source interactive computing infrastructure for research and education. Projects such as Project Jupyter and Pangeo and several NASA communities, such as NASA OpenScapes, have constructed similar infrastructure with overwhelming success. These systems rely on a managed cloud-based infrastructure from providers such as the NASA Science Managed Cloud Environment (SMCE) or 2i2c, who help to minimize the burden on the users for maintaining their own cloud infrastructure. For the CryoCloud project, we chose 2i2c services because they most closely aligned with key open-source science standards, standing by principles of:

1. No vendor lock-in;
2. Cloud-vendor agnostic, open-source tools with the right to replicate infrastructure elsewhere;
3. Direct contribution back to the Jupyter and open science ecosystems;
4. Robust, open documentation of services and infrastructure with transparency of full costs;
5. Responsive technological and administrative support with no hierarchy of customers; and
6. A shared responsibility model that empowers the community to learn cloud development skills and aid in maintaining the infrastructure.

We believe these standards are indispensable for reaching NASA's open-source science goals. SMCE's current model did not meet standards (3), (4), and (5) to the extent needed. 2i2c has built cloud-systems for Cryosphere communities in the past at various Hackweeks, where participating researchers recognized the ease of cloud-based collaboration, but lamented the time-limited computing environment and lack of translation into their existing research pipelines. To address these issues, CryoCloud established a persistent curated cloud-computing environment. In the partnership, 2i2c expert cloud engineers oversee the management of the cloud infrastructure and provide community guidance in its use. The community scientific leads build Cryosphere-specific cloud tutorials, provide training and cloud resources, and solicit feedback to streamline scientific discovery. CryoCloud's system is both stable and long-lasting, maintained by software and cloud engineers to minimize technical hurdles for scientists.

Social and Technological Innovations and Challenges

CryoCloud launched its managed-hub in October 2022 to NASA ICESat-2 Science Team awardees and team members and is slowly expanding the user base to the broader NASA Cryosphere community through a series of workshops at four Cryosphere meetings in the first year. The CryoCloud leadership team is composed of early career researchers with broad scientific expertise and varying levels of cloud and GitHub infrastructure knowledge. The CryoCloud community is bolstered by the support of expert cloud engineers and more technically experienced researchers who can provide specialized expertise and support. In this way, we have been able to rapidly (same day) respond to user issues and needs within the initial group of ~40 users, establishing robust systems to streamline research needs and channels of communication (via the use of Slack, GitHub Issues, Pangeo Discussions board, and community office hours) while the program is in its infancy. We expect to eventually support 300 to 400 users, acquiring user surveys before onboarding and regularly throughout the course of the project to gauge cloud experience levels, motivations, use, needs, and expectations.

Soliciting user feedback reveals patterns of use as researchers learn and adapt to new systems. The feedback we have received thus far has helped us both improve the technology and the social models we need to conduct open-source collaborative science that employs the cloud to its full potential and, therefore, allows new problems to be solved. We have gained valuable insights into the needs and challenges of our users, which predominantly stem from social limitations rather than technological ones. This aligns with our perception that social changes are the largest component of the innovation required to achieve NASA's open science goals:

New, flexible tools are required by the scientific community to improve user experiences, enhance collaboration, and minimize unexpected spending. We have specifically identified the need for tools that enhance inter- and intra-hub sharing and collaboration as well as a cost monitoring gauge to prevent users from unknowingly overspending. Both are expected to be built by 2i2c and added to Jupyter infrastructure over the course of this project. We anticipate future development will address a need for new tools for accessing non-cloud data from data centers, interfacing more easily with High Performance Computing Systems, and meeting federal security standards.

Providing a cloud platform designed for scientific/educational use, to multiple communities, reduces the overall cost and time burden. The research infrastructure that 2i2c provides CryoCloud costs \$27,000 annually. These costs will cover the annual basic research needs of ~300 users, not including the Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2), which for our pilot we have budgeted as \$10,897 annually. Our model reduces computational infrastructure costs to less than one hundred dollars per researcher, showcasing the cost efficiency of this platform.

Users expect to soon be performing most of their computing in the cloud. Our user survey showed that although ~70% of our users use the cloud little to not at all today, >70% expect that they will use the cloud for the majority of their computing five years from now (Figure 1a).

Users' primary motivation for transitioning to the cloud is to eliminate data download and local storage, run analyses faster, and collaborate and develop more easily (Figure 1b). Completing the data transfer of all NASA repositories to the cloud and into cloud-optimized formats will enable the full utilization of the cloud today. We are testing new and thoughtful solutions for data storage that eliminates the redundancy of every user storing the same data copies with the use of a shared S3 bucket and community shared folders. Given the expense for individual users to store data on the cloud, it is vital that NASA continue testing storage solutions and provide shared storage containers.

The user interface must be easy to learn to incentivize user transition into the cloud. The 2i2c JupyterHub meets this need by having a simple authentication method for adding new users via their GitHub credentials and by looking and feeling as similar to the user's own local working platform as possible, whether they are familiar with RStudio, JupyterLab, or another script editor.

Computing infrastructure must be flexible and modular to meet the unique needs of many communities of practice. Infrastructure should have the ability to incorporate different software packages, language kernels (e.g., [corn](#) from NASA OpenScapes), and servers to meet user specific needs and empower users to have autonomy and ownership over their systems.

Cloud training must be immersive to provide incentive for transitioning to the cloud. Users need to have time to open their code and work on the cloud during training workshops to gain enough momentum to transition their workflows, coupled with continued access and support as they build new workflows beyond the training event. This effort has been widely successful in the University of Washington eScience Institute's Hackweeks, where users immerse themselves over the course

Fig. 1. (a) CryoCloud onboarding survey results indicate new users anticipating a greater percentage of their scientific computing being conducted on the cloud five years from now. (b) Survey results indicate users' motivations for transitioning to the cloud using CryoCloud (29 users surveyed).

of a week of practice. Within our initial user base, previous Hackweek participants are the heaviest users on the CryoCloud platform, highlighting the link between immersion and use.

Early career researchers, underrepresented groups, and non-RI academic institution researchers benefit from an established cloud computing environment the most. Transitioning data to the cloud and having a stable environment readily accessible addresses two of the least acknowledged, but most problematic and time-intensive bottlenecks for accomplishing science, particularly for new researchers: building your computing environment and finding and accessing the required data. Having systems like CryoCloud freely available democratizes and accelerates science discovery, allowing all users to have access to reliable, fast, and flexible computing infrastructure that is currently often only accessible by teams at large research institutions.

A shared cloud platform facilitates community building that reduces the software development feedback cycle, accelerates tool development, and helps reduce redundancy/reinventing the wheel within a community of practice. CryoCloud houses developers and users for multiple open science projects and organizations: NASA [Earthaccess](#), the National Snow and Ice Data Center (testing cloud-optimized formats), ICESat-2 SlideRule, and the icepyx library. Developers work alongside users in the same computing environment, allowing for instant collaboration, testing, and feedback that accelerates development and use. Within a common cloud environment, developers and users across communities can pool resources, communicate and collaborate easily, and are therefore better able to divide and conquer outstanding gaps in infrastructure and science, rather than competing or working in isolation.

A consistent platform provides a place where individuals and communities can rapidly mobilize when need arises. A standing platform makes it seamless to bring underserved communities into the cloud and allows teams or communities to gather and collaborate in response to climate emergencies, for educational events, or shared initiatives with a small amount of planning or resources. Rapid mobilization of individuals and teams allows for more efficient responses to scientific problems, delivering solutions to first-responders and policy-makers on timelines that can impact decision-making. In this way, CryoCloud saves Cryosphere communities more than \$75,000 per year in cloud infrastructure costs because it serves as the computing platform for the following events: eScience [ICESat-2](#) and [SnowEx](#) Hackweeks (~80 users each) for Cryosphere

education and training, and an [NSF QGreenland](#) community workshop for developing Cryosphere data access and integrating Cryosphere and indigenous communities.

NASA's Role in the Open Science Future

Social innovation will be critical for reaching our open science goals. NASA can generalize from the patterns, principals, and infrastructure built by communities like CryoCloud to implement cloud-computing ecosystems across all NASA communities and steer scientific innovation to a collaborative and more unified future. To facilitate the transformation to a wholly open science future, *we suggest that certain procedures become policy.*

Aside from the standards and lessons mentioned above, NASA can accelerate open science through improved collaboration and a unification of data standards by the DAACs. CryoCloud users experience friction while using the cloud from cumbersome and separate authentication methods, outdated and complex data formats, and a firehose of data standards that create substantial barriers to data fusion and must all be learned by the user. DAAC resource compatibility and interoperability can fully unlock the potential of cloud resources by transitioning to cloud-optimized data formats and streamlined data production while helping to create shared community practices that work towards a model that facilitates science, not just hosts datasets. Failure to deliver interoperability between infrastructure and data hinders research progress.

Providing a cloud-computing platform as a service from NASA that adheres to Principles 1-6 above is a straightforward path towards sharing information across communities, reducing community cloud costs, and building towards clear objectives in NASA's science mission. Future models for providing cloud services may include creative solutions, such as NASA building an on-prem cloud service for storage and general computing on small servers (majority of compute time) that can outsource to industry providers for larger compute services.

NASA can also help the larger academic incentive system to shift to directly value contributions to software development and open-source science and move further from the deeply ingrained 'publish or perish' mentality that often feeds into predatory for-profit publishing or rushed, repetitious research work. Through the addition of requirements in the grant solicitation and review process, creating recommendation lists, and mandating minimal training modules, NASA can incentivize using publishers, providers, and science/data patterns that adhere to specific open science standards. Similarly, NASA could incentivize institutional shifts to open science tenure systems by giving higher scoring criteria to these institutions in review processes.

Vision for the Future

Two immediate needs for enabling open science are to provide cloud-computing infrastructure on a persistent basis and to effectively train scientists for a transition to this new analysis platform. Projects like CryoCloud introduce researchers to the capabilities of cloud computing (a suite of curated tools and easily accessed data) while also demonstrating the enhanced collaboration potential of cloud workflows. Collaborative research enabled by cloud computing will unleash synergies and deliver research products of a larger and more impactful scale and scope than is possible with current outmoded workflows. Through such open and collaborative cloud frameworks, knowledge becomes less diffusive and more convective, bringing insights quickly to the forefront to inform actions rather than being stuck behind publisher paywalls or the academic research pipeline. CryoCloud arose from a desire to build a more collaborative and innovative future than our current model. Creating a generic, open ecosystem, capable of meeting the data and computational needs of a NASA community of practice, goes beyond computing architecture to an interactive and iterative environment that requires both social and technical innovation.